

I. PREPARATION FOR THE PELLETS

Weigh each of the following excipients in a disposable mixing vial similar to the SpectroVial shown below (equivalent disposable mixing vials can be used). Each will contain a total of ~5.0 grams.

Weights for each 5g Pellet								
Excipients	Formulation 1 (grams)	Formulation 2 (grams)	Formulation 3 (grams)	Formulation 4 (grams)	Formulation 5 (grams)	Formulation 6 (grams)	Formulation 7 (grams)	Formulation 8 (grams)
Microcrystalline Cellulose	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
Magnesium Aluminum Silicate	0.25	0.30	0.50	0.40	0.40	0.50	0.35	0.20
Lactose	2.65	2.65	2.35	2.40	2.50	2.40	2.50	2.50
Starch	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Stearic Acid	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Red Ferric Oxide	0.25	0.20	0.25	0.25	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.10
Silicon Dioxide	0.04	0.05	0.12	0.15	0.23	0.30	0.35	0.40
Total	4.99	5.00	5.02	5.00	4.98	5.00	5.00	5.00

Spectro-Vial (Chemplex Cat.no. 1134)

Ball pestles (Chemplex cat. no. 1211)

II. PREPARATION FOR THE SPIKING SOLUTIONS

Information:

Final Target Levels for Standards in 5 Gram Pellets:

	Formulation 1	Formulation 2	Formulation 3	Formulation 4	Formulation 5	Formulation 6	Formulation 7	Formulation 8
RECOMMENDED Spiking Levels (ppm)								
Cd	1.5	3	5	10	3	15	1.5	7.5
Pb	1.5	3	5	10	15	7.5	1.5	3
As	4.5	30	15	9	9	45	4.5	22.5
Hg	9	18	30	60	18	90	9	45
Co	15	30	50	100	30	150	15	75
V	30	60	100	200	60	300	30	150
Ni	60	120	200	400	120	600	60	300

Element	Stock Solution (ppm)	Diluted Solution (ppm)
Cd	1000	100
Pb	1000	100
As	1000	100
Hg	1000	100
Co	10,000	1000
V	10,000	1000
Ni	10,000	1000

Obtain the above Class 1 and 2A ICP standards and do a 1:10 dilution for each.

III. SPIKING SOLUTIONS INTO PRE-WEIGHED FORMULATIONS

Spike the formulations as prescribed below for each of the pre-weighed formulations in Step I. Make a little divet or well in the powder and spike the following ICP standards directly into the well (avoid the solution touching the sides of the vial, if possible).

Formulation 1

Element	Volume (uL)	Solution Conc (ppm)	Final Conc (ppm) in 5 gram pre-weighed Formulation
Cd	75	100	1.5
Pb	75	100	1.5
As	225	100	4.5
Hg	45	1000	9.0
Co	75	1000	15
V	150	1000	30
Ni	300	1000	60

Formulation 2

Element	Volume (uL)	Solution Conc (ppm)	Final Conc (ppm) in 5 gram pre-weighed Formulation
Cd	15	1000	3
Pb	15	1000	3
As	150	1000	30
Hg	90	1000	18
Co	15	10000	30
V	30	10000	60
Ni	60	10000	120

Formulation 3

Element	Volume (uL)	Solution Conc (ppm)	Final Conc (ppm) in 5 gram pre-weighed Formulation
Cd	25	1000	5
Pb	25	1000	5
As	75	1000	15
Hg	150	1000	30
Co	25	10000	50
V	50	10000	100
Ni	100	10000	200

Formulation 4

Element	Volume (uL)	Solution Conc (ppm)	Final Conc (ppm) in 5 gram pre-weighed Formulation
Cd	50	1000	10
Pb	50	1000	10
As	45	1000	9
Hg	300	1000	60
Co	50	10000	100
V	100	10000	200
Ni	200	10000	400

Formulation 5

Element	Volume (uL)	Solution Conc (ppm)	Final Conc (ppm) in 5 gram pre-weighed Formulation
Cd	15	1000	3
Pb	75	1000	15
As	45	1000	9
Hg	90	1000	18
Co	15	10000	30
V	30	10000	60
Ni	60	10000	120

Formulation 6

Element	Volume (uL)	Solution Conc (ppm)	Final Conc (ppm) in 5 gram pre-weighed Formulation
Cd	75	1000	15
Pb	37.5	1000	7.5
As	225	1000	45
Hg	450	1000	90
Co	75	10000	150
V	150	10000	300
Ni	300	10000	600

Formulation 7

Element	Volume (uL)	Solution Conc (ppm)	Final Conc (ppm) in 5 gram pre-weighed Formulation
Cd	75	100	1.5
Pb	75	100	1.5
As	225	100	4.5
Hg	45	1000	9
Co	75	1000	15
V	150	1000	30
Ni	300	1000	60

Formulation 8

Element	Volume (uL)	Solution Conc (ppm)	Final Conc (ppm) in 5 gram pre-weighed Formulation
Cd	37.5	1000	7.5
Pb	15	1000	3
As	112.5	1000	22.5
Hg	225	1000	45
Co	37.5	10000	75
V	75	10000	150
Ni	150	10000	300

IV. PREPARATION OF PRESSED PELLET

Place the Spectro-vial and dry all formulation/standards in an oven or vacuum oven until thoroughly dried:

Add disposable acrylic balls to mixing vials, cap and mix thoroughly (5 minute mixing time) with a mixing mill:

Remove acrylic balls and add entire remaining contents to a 35 mm die (or appropriate) and press a pellet at 20 Tons for 1 minute

Transfer "*ENTIRE*"
sample to die
assembly

Pellet in Holder

V. SETTING UP QUANTITATIVE CALIBRATION METHOD

Empirical or FP methods can be tried – Empirical is straightforward.

The following describes some details on setting up an FP calibration – Software should allow a user to switch between FP and Empirical

Start a new Quant method and choose model as FP (fundamental Parameters)

Enter ALL calibration standards including the excipients in the formulation (you may need to enter various materials into a compound table (examples Red Iron Oxide, lactose, etc.). Certain ingredients will be measured and others can be labelled as fixed or balance components. Obviously the analytes (metals of interest) will be entered and reported as ppm and the various excipients as mass %.

Application Name Input

Name of application: PQRI-2 FP Method

Type of analysis: Empirical Fundamental parameter method

Description of application:

Folder: USP

Component Selection

Type of component to add: Element Oxide Special compound

Component	Unit	Analysis
1 MCC	mass%	Fixed
2 Veegum	mass%	Measure(FP)
3 Lactose	mass%	Balance
4 Starch	mass%	Fixed
5 Stearic	mass%	Fixed
6 Red Iron	mass%	Measure(FP)
7 SiO2	mass%	Measure(FP)
8 Cd	ppm	Measure(FP)
9 Pb	ppm	Measure(FP)
10 As	ppm	Measure(FP)
11 Hg	ppm	Measure(FP)
12 Co	ppm	Measure(FP)
13 V	ppm	Measure(FP)
14 Ni	ppm	Measure(FP)
15		

The following is just an example of a fictitious summary table:

Actual tables for these entered formulations may vary depending on how you set it up

Standard Samples

Display interlocks

Name	Note	MCC mass%	Veegum mass%	Lactose mass%	Starch mass%	Stearic mass%	Red Iron mass%	SiO2 mass%	Cd ppm	Pb ppm	As ppm	Hg ppm	Co ppm	V ppm	Ni ppm	Analyzed Date
1	Formulation 1	15	5	Balance	20	1	5	0.8	1.5	1.5	4.5	9	15	30	60	
2	Formulation 2	15	6	Balance	20	1	4	1	3	3	30	18	30	60	120	
3	Formulation 3	15	10	Balance	20	1	5	2.3	5	5	15	30	50	100	200	
4	Formulation 4	15	8	Balance	20	1	5	3	10	10	9	60	100	200	400	
5	Formulation 5	15	8	Balance	20	1	1	4.5	3	15	9	18	30	60	120	
6	Formulation 6	15	10	Balance	20	1	0	6	15	7.5	45	90	150	300	600	
7	Formulation 7	15	7	Balance	20	1	0	7	1.5	1.5	4.5	9	15	30	60	
8	Formulation 8	15	4	Balance	20	1	2	8	7.5	3	22.5	45	75	150	300	
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Composition Information

Typical composition of application

	Component	Unit	Typical value
1	MCC	mass%	15.0000
2	Veegum	mass%	7.2500
3	Lactose	mass%	Balance
4	Starch	mass%	20.0000
5	Stearic	mass%	1.0000
6	Red Iron	mass%	2.7500
7	SiO2	mass%	4.0750
8	Cd	ppm	5.8125
9	Pb	ppm	5.8125
10	As	ppm	17.4375
11	Hg	ppm	34.8750
12	Co	ppm	58.1250
13	V	ppm	116.2500
14	Ni	ppm	232.5000

Total conc. 100.0000 mass%

The next step will be to optimize measuring/instrument analysis conditions and run standards:

After running the standards, calibrations of Measured vs Theoretical Intensities are produced:

Unknown samples can now be analyzed containing a varied matrix with this “universal” FP method. This method will give results for not only the desired analytes (Cd, As, Pb, etc.), but also the matrix components

NOTE: prepare the unknown samples exactly as how the standards were prepared (i.e. 5 g weight, 35mm pressed pellet at 20 tons/1min). Analyze against the quantitative calibration curves.